

SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE PRACTICING PSYCHOLOGISTS

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ABSTRACT

In the article, the problem of analyzing the pedagogical point of view on the concept of communicative competence is emphasized. In particular, attention is paid to the definitions and interpretations of communicative competence provided by teachers, as well as the impact of these definitions on the professional competence of teachers. In addition, the article examines the components and dimensions of communicative competence based on the analysis of educational materials.

Key words: competence, communicative, communicative competence, communicative knowledge, communicative ability, communicative skill, communication skills, social perception.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье подчеркивается проблема анализа педагогического взгляда на понятие коммуникативной компетентности. В частности, уделяется внимание определениям и трактовкам коммуникативной компетентности, которые дают учителя, а также влиянию этих определений на профессиональную компетентность учителей. Кроме того, в статье на основе анализа учебных материалов рассматриваются компоненты и измерения коммуникативной компетентности.

Ключевые слова: компетентность, коммуникативность, коммуникативная компетентность, коммуникативные знания, коммуникативная способность, коммуникативные умения, коммуникативные способности, социальное восприятие.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, there is a demand for a fundamental revision of the requirements for education and technology-based education and its results. Consequently, the creation of new generation standards has become a crucial task for pedagogues. Current national education standards are systematic and active-led, and they aim to define the purpose of educational modules in terms of imparting knowledge, skills and competences. However, there is now a

demand to focus these new state education standards on the development of competent and active leadership. This shift emphasizes the need to focus not only on the development of students' needs and skills, but also on the transfer of knowledge, skills and abilities in informational and verbal form. To increase students' experience of practical activity, it is not enough to provide knowledge only in the reproductive method. Consequently, students collect excessive, irrelevant information, which leads to ineffectiveness of education and its inconsistency with reality.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

In order to solve the above-mentioned problems, it is considered necessary to build educational processes on the basis of various innovative approaches. The views of our Honorable President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev on raising independent thinking and high intellectual and moral potential among our youth, ensuring that they become mature individuals in various fields on a global scale are also noteworthy. Therefore, organizing lessons based on modern, innovative approaches that meet the requirements of the new era is one of our most important tasks as pedagogues. The only way to overcome these challenges is to modernize education and implement competent leadership. Perfect leadership requires students not only to acquire knowledge and skills, but also to master them thoroughly. Consequently, the system of selecting teaching methods undergoes changes to meet the requirements for teaching competencies and functions.[1]

First of all, it is necessary to clarify the meaning of the term "competence". Competence (I use the Latin term because it is the most accurate translation) means the subject's ability to effectively use internal and external resources to achieve a certain goal, or in other words, it is a personal ability. solving problems related to a specific object of activity. It should be noted that most of the definitions given to the concept of "competence" are related to professional education and professional activities. However, due to the innovative nature of general education, there is a special need to define its essence.[2]

Competence is derived from the Latin word "Competentia" and in Uzbek it means "to be knowledgeable", "to have experience". Competence refers to the ability to perform a task effectively, to meet the demands of the task, and to meet the specific functional requirements of the task. Professional competence is the acquisition and application of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for a specialist to perform professional activities at a high level of competence.[3]

L.M. Mitina pedagogical competence includes scientific knowledge, teaching methodology and didactics, pedagogical communication skills, as well as self-development, self-improvement, self-realization methods and tools includes. When constructing pedagogical competence, he distinguishes three main components: activity-based, communicative and personal. In accordance with the proposal of L.M. Mitina on the systematization of pedagogical competence, we consider the following set of competencies that are sufficient and necessary for the level of development of pedagogical competence for future specialists: - specific or special pedagogical competence (knowledge, skills and individual methods of their implementation). pedagogical activity); - personal or professional competence (knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for self-improvement and self-realization); - communicative competence (knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for creative implementation of pedagogical activity); Concepts of professionalism and competence have common features.[4]

It should be noted that persons who fully comply with the established requirements and standards do not become qualified specialists, because some do not have the ability to apply knowledge in practice, which makes their pedagogical activity ineffective.

The purpose of dividing professional pedagogical competencies into different types:

- special pedagogical competence;
- to have sufficient information for effective implementation of pedagogical activities. In addition, the evaluation of one's professional level as a teacher and the determination of development as a specialist belong to this type;
- social pedagogical competence;
- determines the teacher's ability to establish effective relationships with colleagues, coordinate joint actions, take responsibility for joint actions. Adequate communication skills, pedagogical culture and responsibility for work results;
- all these are included in the concept of social pedagogical competence;
- personal pedagogical competence;
- the ability to rationally organize pedagogical work, manage time, and cope with personal development are the main components of personal pedagogical competence.

Workers with high personal pedagogical skills are less prone to stress and able to work under time pressure.[5]

Qualities of teacher's professional competence:

- ☐ Formation of motivation in students
- ☐ Ability to plan, evaluate, and establish feedback on the educational process
- ☐ Knowledge of information and communication technologies
- ☐ Work on yourself
- ☐ Having knowledge of pedagogy and psychology
- ☐ Excellent knowledge of his subject
- ☐ Bringing innovation to the educational environment

Professional competence can include competence in professional activities, competence in professional communication, competence of a specialist in being able to demonstrate his profession. After understanding what competence is, it is not difficult to determine its levels.

A.A. Competence in professional communication by Derkach:

- communicative competence (ability to communicate with colleagues),
- social-perceptive competence (the ability to perceive and evaluate other people),
- differential and psychological competence (differentiation of individual psychological differences between people),
- diagnostic competence (the ability to learn the characteristics of other people),
- moral competence (compliance with the norms of ethics appropriate to this profession),
- empathic competence (empathizing with team members, understanding them correctly and distinguishing other components).[6]

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be said that not only providing education to the learner, but also the teacher's psychological readiness for pedagogical activity is very important in providing education and training to a person. In such cases, it is necessary to pay special attention to the level of professional competence of the teacher. Competent approach in the educational system, acceptance as a conceptual basis of educational reforms, introduction of a competent approach to the educational system, educational purpose, content, form of teaching, teaching methods, pedagogical and information technologies, control methods and requires significant changes in the roles of the teacher and the learner. Fundamental changes should be made in pedagogical higher education in order to accumulate the professional competence of the teacher. At a time when

certain works are being carried out in the direction of improving the state educational standard, curriculum and textbooks of higher education, although it is difficult to abandon the existing traditional content, it is necessary to further clarify the content of education.

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